

SACRIFICING INNOVATION IN ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE (AI) ON THE ALTAR OF REGULATION: NIGERIA AS A CASE STUDY*

ABSTRACT

The introduction of Artificial Intelligence (AI) was welcomed by state and non-state actors because of the possibilities that could be actualised with the use of this 'new system'. Just like the internet, the introduction of AI to the global landscape was not intended to be used to perpetrate ills or to violate the rights of persons. However, scars left from the unscrupulous use of technological innovations have raised fears from various quarters that this new system may fall into the wrong hands, causing greater evil than the intended good. These fears, though legitimate, have formed the basis for the formulation of restrictive regulations which in turn have hampered innovation in AI. To this end, this paper sets out to argue in favour of the innovations that can be developed from AI systems and the need for this system to be given full expression before the lawmakers can step in to formulate laws geared towards curtailing the potential mischief that may characterise the use of AI systems, rather than addressing merely perceived issues.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence; Innovation; Regulations; Algorithm

1.0 INTRODUCTION

There is no doubt that the introduction of Artificial Intelligence (AI) to our ecosystem has led to advancement in various sectors that directly affect the lives of the citizens and governance. Despite the prospect of a more advanced world with AI, many fear that it lacks accuracy and the requisite fairness. These concerns have led to calls for regulations.¹ While these regulations are desirable, there is a need to determine the best time to regulate AI systems after observing their potential to a great extent.

To rush into an outright ban or overregulation of AI would result in not only a delay in the introduction of innovative ideas but can discourage inventiveness and innovation and an undue restriction to societal advancement. Eric Schmidt has described this to be the “chilling effect”², which can be illustrated thus: *when a start-up has an innovative idea with the AI system and is faced with regulations that are hard to make meaning of, the proprietors of the start-up would be discouraged from going forward with the innovative idea because they either do not want to be in breach of the law, or they cannot afford the services of lawyers that are capable of making sense of the regulation.*

The argument posed by this paper does not intend to undermine the relevance of laws in curtailing bad practices with the use of AI systems. We only intend to demonstrate the need for state and non-state actors to lean towards AI Governance/Ethics as the first point of call before

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¹ B. Ziegler, “Is It Time To Regulate AI?” Available online at <https://www.wsj.com/articles/is-it-time-to-regulate-ai-11649433600>. (Accessed 7 October, 2022).

² H. A. Kissinger, E. Schmidt, and D. Huttenlocher: The Age of AI: And Our Human Future, *New York: Little Brown & Company*, 2021.

regulating the system. We believe that by making ethical considerations the centre of discourse, many of the fears would be allayed and innovations would flourish.

Hence, this paper is set out as follows: Introduction; How AI works and its endless possibilities; the ethical considerations with the use of AI; when the best time to regulate AI is; Nigeria and AI; Conclusion and Recommendations.

The introductory part would be concluded with a clarification of the following concepts:

“Artificial Intelligence”

Refers to those techniques that allow computers to learn, reason, infer, communicate and make decisions that in the past were the sole province of humans.³

“AI Algorithms”

This connotes an extended subset of machine learning that tells the computer how to learn to operate on its own.

“Robotics”

Robotics is often used interchangeably with AI. However, it is best to treat them as distinct concepts because the former is a branch of the latter. Hence, Robotics can be defined as the branch of AI that deals with the design, construction, operation, and application of robots to perform tasks done traditionally by human beings.⁴

2.0 HOW AI WORKS AND ITS ENDLESS POSSIBILITIES

Some of the world's most popular movies, like Terminator, Matrix, Avengers and Star Wars, are filled with Sci-Fi plots in which computers are portrayed to have the ability to think independently or, as they sometimes represent, surpass human intelligence and even replicate themselves. In some of these movies, machines have a mind of their own so much so that they attack humans. Although those storylines may be fictional, they depict what AI entails.

The history of AI goes as far back as the time of philosophers. AI has always been conceptualised in different forms in myths, legends and tales. In the 19th century, some authors incorporated “thinking machines” into fictional books⁵. However, the watershed in the development of AI came in 1950 when Alan Turing — the scientist that invented the Bombe, a machine used to decipher the German Enigma codes during World War II — wrote a paper titled *Computing Machinery and Intelligence*. In this paper, he envisaged computers that could use available information to generate solutions and make decisions like humans⁶. He also devised a “Turing

³ *Supra* note 1.

⁴ B. A. Schreiber, “Robotics”. Available online at <https://www.britannica.com/technology/robotics>. (Accessed 7 October, 2022).

⁵ Wikipedia, “History of artificial intelligence” Available online at https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/History_of_artificial_intelligence. (Accessed October 6, 2022).

⁶ LabXchange, “The History of Artificial Intelligence” Available online at <https://www.labxchange.org/library/items/lb:LabXchange:0c0b0290.html:1?source=%2Flibrary%2Fclusters%2Fcluster%3Aaabe->

Test” in his article setting standards to test if a computer is capable of exhibiting human intelligence. This formed the vision that propelled the development of AI as we know it today.

AI has evolved into different subfields — Machine Learning (ML), Deep Learning (DL), Natural Language Processing and Computer Vision. The most commonly used of these are ML and DL. ML uses statistical methods to process massive volumes of data without the need for human interaction⁷ while DL is a kind of machine learning that employs enormous datasets and artificial neural networks to imitate the operation of the brain and identify patterns that may be used to make decisions.⁸ These various subfields are combined and applied in healthcare, transportation, finance, education, marketing and many areas of human endeavours.

At the base of the operations of AI is Data. Algorithms, which are the building blocks of AI, are created to perform certain instructions on data supplied. In a world of Big Data, AI is deployed to handle the expansive amount of data impossible for a human to handle. The quality of output of an AI system is premised on the quality of data supplied to it and the algorithm that runs it. Therefore, it is prone to reproduce human biases reflected in human data. For example, an AI system used in hiring may favour white people over other races because of the data supplied to it and the algorithm it operates with.

Some also believe that AI can be used for illegal or unethical purposes. How data is received processed, used and transferred is a source of huge concern to many. AI could be used to invade privacy or to commit crimes with transnational consequences.

These do not, however, take away the gigantic potential of AI. Already, a lot of mundane tasks are left in the hands of high-performance machines. With AI, the possibility of inventing cutting-edge solutions in healthcare and other areas of human endeavour is now a reality. Alexa now helps to find your way to the nearest coffee shop. Applications are built that recommend investment strategies based on data collected on a person’s investment patterns. Many use Google Assistant, Bixby or Siri on their smartphones and PCs. These are instances where AI is making human life easier.

It must be noted that the prophecies in fictional movies where machines attack humans on their own accord are highly unlikely. As said earlier, at the base of every AI system are algorithms created by humans. Therefore, any action by AI is human-driven.

3.0 THE ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS SURROUNDING THE USE OF AI

Having considered the endless possibilities that could be realised with AI, we acknowledge the need for AI systems to be governed by ethical standards that guides their development, use and functionalities. AI is a tool to make human living much easier and more productive, however as

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⁷ ProjectPro, “Machine Learning (ML) vs NLP - What's the Difference?” Available online at <https://www.projectpro.io/article/machine-learning-vs-nlp/493#:~:text=Machine%20learning%20is%20often%20used,of%20a%20sentence%20or%20words>. (Accessed October 6, 2022).

⁸ *Ibid.*

earlier mentioned, it can be deployed to commit atrocities by persons who have ill intentions. The government is then compelled to regulate every idea and innovation stemming from AI to protect the public interest. However, to prevent premature regulations of AI, we advocate for policy formulations that reflect these ethical standards discussed below.

The European Commission published The Ethics Guidelines in April 2019 which provide that AI technologies must be *Trustworthy*.⁹ Trustworthy AI according to the Commission should be:

- (1) Lawful - respecting all applicable laws and regulations
- (2) Ethical - respecting ethical principles and values¹⁰
- (3) Robust - both from a technical perspective while taking into account its social environment.

The Commission further sets 7 (seven) basic requirements that ensure these standards are met.¹¹ For this paper, the emphasis would be placed on five issues surrounding the ethics of AI.

3.1 THE ISSUES SURROUNDING ETHICS AND ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE¹²

3.1.1 Artificial Intelligence and the Protection of Human Rights

Artificial Intelligence can be used for a lot of good in society but it can be catastrophic if they are applied without regard to human rights. Human dignity, Right to Privacy, and Freedom of Expression are rights that should be protected throughout the lifecycle of an AI Innovation.

Human dignity encompasses the idea that every human being possesses an “intrinsic worth”, which should never be diminished, compromised or repressed by others – nor by new technologies like AI systems.¹³

AI systems should hence be developed in a manner that respects, serves and protects humans’ physical and mental integrity, personal and cultural sense of identity, and satisfaction of their essential needs.¹⁴

The right to freedom of expression and choice are also intrinsic rights of every individual which must not be compromised throughout the lifecycle of an AI system. This freedom in an AI context includes freedom from indirect coercion, threats to mental health, unjustified surveillance,

⁹ AI HLEG, “Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI” (2019). Available online at <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-singlemarket/en/news/ethics-guidelines-trustworthy-ai>. (Accessed October 9, 2022).

¹⁰ The principles which underscore the ethics of AI cannot be considered in isolation from its values as the values reflect the ethos of the society in respect of which the AI system is developed and sought to operate.

¹¹ These requirements reflect the values and principles embodied in UNESCO’s Recommendations on the Ethics of Artificial Intelligence. See the UNESCO, “Recommendation of the Ethics on Artificial Intelligence”. Available online at https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000380455_locale=en. (Accessed October 9, 2022).

¹² Please note that the ethical issues surrounding Artificial Intelligence are inexhaustive and are dynamic hence they may change over time and the number of ethical considerations may increase or decrease as the need arises.

¹³ C. McCrudden, “Human Dignity and Judicial Interpretation of Human Rights”, *IILJ Working Paper 2008/8* Finalized 10/03/08. Available online at <https://iilj.org/wp-content/uploads/2016/08/McCrudden-Human-Dignity-and-Judicial-Interpretation-of-Human-Rights-2008-1.pdf>. (Accessed 9 October, 2022).

¹⁴ P. Inverardi, “The Challenge of Human Dignity in the Era of Autonomous Systems”, *Perspectives on Digital Humanism*. Available online at <https://dighum.ec.tuwien.ac.at/perspectives-on-digital-humanism/the-challenge-of-human-dignity-in-the-era-of-autonomous-systems/> (Accessed 9 October, 2022).

deception and unfair manipulation, amongst others. The EU Commission encapsulates all areas of freedom in this context as follows:

“Freedom of the individual means a commitment to enabling individuals to wield even higher control over their lives, including (among other rights) protection of the freedom to conduct a business, the freedom of the arts and science, freedom of expression, the right to private life and privacy, and freedom of assembly and association.”¹⁵

Privacy is a right that is essential to the protection of human dignity, human autonomy and Human agency.¹⁶ Data obtained for AI technologies must be collected, used, shared and deleted in accordance with laws that provide for the protection of the human right to privacy. Data received from people should not be used to unlawfully or unfairly discriminate against them.

Access to data must also be regulated. In any organisation handling data, protocols must be in place to govern data access, who can access such data and the circumstances that warrant such access. Data received must be treated with all sense of prudence, respect and caution.

3.1.2 Artificial Intelligence and Transparency

The processes that yield the AI system’s decision as well as the decisions resulting from those processes must be documented in detail to ensure transparency and traceability. Where AI systems affect people’s lives significantly, their process should be traceable and transparent. This will increase confidence in the system and give room for public scrutiny.

Transparency also includes Communication and Explicability. AI systems should not represent themselves as humans because humans have the right to be informed that they are interacting with an AI system.¹⁷

3.1.3 Artificial Intelligence and Human Oversight

Due to the many complexities accompanying AI, ethical and legal responsibility for any stage in the life cycle of AI systems must be attributable to physical or existing legal entities. Public oversight may also be required in appropriate circumstances. Human Oversight and Interference must be included in an AI system to ensure that human autonomy is not undermined. Oversight may be achieved through the introduction of mechanisms such as a human-in-the-loop (HITL), Human-on-the-loop (HOTL) or Human-in-command (HIC). While HITL (which implies the direct intervention of humans in every decision of the system) is almost impossible and is not desirable, HOTL (which refers to human intervention in the design cycle) and HIC (which is the capacity of humans to oversee the entire activity of the AI and to determine when and how to use the system) are most preferable.

¹⁵ *Supra* note 9

¹⁶ *Supra* note 11

¹⁷ This is an offshoot of the right of every individual to freedom of expression and choice.

It has also been asserted that *“the less oversight a human can exercise over an AI system, the more extensive testing and stricter governance is required.”*

3.1.4 Artificial Intelligence and Environmental and Societal Well-being

AI systems are created to benefit human beings including the future generation. Societal relationships, development and impact must be critically considered in the construction of AI systems. While AI systems can be used to enhance social skills, they could also deteriorate people’s physical and mental well-being.¹⁸ The impact of an AI system on institutions, democracy and society at large must also be carefully scrutinised.

AI systems must also be developed to protect the environment. A critical analysis of the present and future impact of AI technologies on our environment must be carried out regularly to ensure the sustainability of the environment for the present and future generations.

3.1.5 Artificial Intelligence and Ensuring Diversity, Non-Discrimination and Fairness

Errors in the construction or use of an AI system can lead to bias and discrimination. Harm can also result from the intentional exploitation of (consumer) biases or by engaging in unfair competition, such as the homogenization of prices through collusion or a non-transparent market.¹⁹

This could be resolved by putting in place oversight processes to analyse and address the system’s purpose, constraints, requirements and decisions clearly and transparently. Moreover, hiring from diverse backgrounds, cultures and disciplines can ensure diversity of opinions and should be encouraged.²⁰

4.0 WHEN THE BEST TIME TO REGULATE AI IS

A divide exists between those advocating for AI regulation and others who say that regulations at this formative stage would be premature. Elon Musk and Stephen Hawking who are notable figures in the science and technology industry in the United States of America (USA) favour the regulation of AI at this early stage.²¹ Elon Musk in one of his tweets observed as follows, *“Got to regulate AI/robotics like we do food, drugs, aircraft & cars. Public risks require public oversight.”*²²

On the other hand, Andrew Burt, an executive at a data management company in the USA, Immuta argues that regulating an assemblage of technology we cannot clearly define is a recipe for poor laws and the emergence of worse technology.²³ He further observed that the challenges

¹⁸ *Supra* note 9 at page 20

¹⁹ EU Agency for Fundamental Rights’ paper: “BigData: Discrimination in data-supported decision making”, 2018. Available online at <http://fra.europa.eu/en/publication/2018/big-data-discrimination>. (Accessed 9 October, 2022).

²⁰ *Supra* note 9 at page 18

²¹ M. Beishon, “Is it Time to Regulate AI?”. *InterMEDIA | December/January 2018 Vol 45 Issue 4*. Available online at <https://www.iicom.org/wp-content/uploads/im-jan018-artificial-intelligence-2.pdf>. (Accessed 9 October, 2022).

²² The tweet can be found online at <https://twitter.com/elonmusk/status/934889932807593984?s=46&t=rZiKrB2422Zw8M4FkJsA>. (Accessed 9 October, 2022).

²³ A. Burt, “Leave AI Alone” (2018). *New York Times*, 4 January, 2018.

of AI are not new, as we have long been using automated systems in various sectors like finance where a similar issue of data privacy was encountered.

It is the norm to expect government regulation when a product is likely to cause harm to the end user. But AI systems, are often not designed for end users but somehow have a way of directly affecting the lives of the populace as it relates to their privacy, inequality and societal development, amongst others. Furthermore, we are not sure of the extent to which AI systems can go in terms of posing a threat to members of society, hence an attempt to formulate a regulation would only render it premature.

We believe that it is preferable to have preventive mechanisms in place and overseen by a body set up to observe the AI system to determine the best approach to regulating it.²⁴ This is the approach adopted by the USA Chamber of Commerce which launched its AI Commission on Competitiveness, Inclusion and Innovation.

Additionally, rather than formulating a holistic regulation governing the subject, we believe that sector-specific regulations would be more effective at least in the interim, pending a reasonable development of AI systems. This is because the issues posed by AI lie significantly in the data fed to it.²⁵ Also, because some sectors are more critical than others, problems may arise if AI is deployed first before regulating it. For instance, in the field of medicine, the manufacturing of drugs and the development of new treatments must first satisfy regulatory standards.

Hence, to answer the question of the best time to regulate AI, due consideration must be given to the surrounding circumstances. The best time would certainly be when the mischief that may be occasioned by the use of AI is uncovered to a great degree.

5.0 NIGERIA AND AI

Nigeria is the most populous country in Africa with a burgeoning young population. The young population of Nigeria has driven development in the technology sector of Nigeria, making Nigeria a fast-rising player in the continent. From 2021 - 2022, Nigeria's tech startups raised more money than any other country in Africa.²⁶

AI is largely uncharted territory in Africa and Nigeria, especially in the public sector. However, AI is reckoned to be the next major revolution in the economy and society even in Nigeria. The country has consequently taken steps to encourage the development of AI. Nigeria established a National Centre for Artificial Intelligence and Robotics (NCAIR) in 2020 to foster research, development and incorporation of AI in Nigeria. Nigeria can, therefore, be considered to be AI-friendly and a step ahead of many other African Countries in that regard.

²⁴ *Supra* note 1.

²⁵ The Royal Society and British Academy Report, 2017 titled "Data Management and Use: Governance in the 21st Century" propose that while AI will generate some specific challenges, it would not be helpful to see AI governance as something unrelated to and separate from broader data governance. British Academy, Royal Society (2017). Data management and use: governance in the 21st century.

²⁶ Africa: The Big deal, "Ecosystem on a roll". Available online at <https://thebigdeal.substack.com/p/ecosystem-on-a-roll->. (Accessed October 12, 2022).

Nigeria is also set to formulate a National AI Policy (NAIP). The Federal Ministry of Communications and Digital Economy directed the National Information Technology Development Agency (NITDA) to develop the policy to ensure that Nigeria harnesses the endless possibilities AI has to offer in the economic development of Nigeria. NITDA has in turn begun to call for collaborative efforts to ensure a comprehensive and well-thought policy that will not stifle development in the nascent AI space in Nigeria.²⁷

It must be noted that there exists a framework for data management in Nigeria and it also regulates AI because data is the fuel of AI. The Nigeria Data Protection Regulations (NDPR) and subsequent Guidelines for the management of personal data by Public Institutions in Nigeria released by NITDA presently represent the regulatory framework for data management.

We believe that the regulatory attitude of Nigeria towards AI is commendable. By creating regulations instead of full-blown legislation, a flexible regulatory framework is created to accommodate the rapid changes in the AI space globally and Nigeria. Statutes and laws must go through the sometimes rigorous and sluggish formal process of amendment. This can prove counterproductive to accelerated innovation in the AI space in Nigeria which must be allowed to fully blossom unhindered. Regulations created by sector-specific regulator engenders a responsive and informed regulatory framework that both accommodates beneficial disruptive change and also mitigates the possible risks.

Furthermore, regulators and the largely tech-illiterate population of Nigeria must be given time to understand the complexities of AI and the legal and ethical implications surrounding the incorporation of AI into the daily lives of Nigerians. Then and only then can a comprehensive statutory framework be enacted that will not overregulate the emerging technology and suppress its development and adoption.

6.0 CONCLUSION

In the era of Big Data, some tasks are too complicated and massive to be done efficiently and accurately by humans. AI technologies have gradually become a necessity in our everyday lives due to the ease and convenience it avails us of. There are however certain issues that have raised doubts as to its safety and reliability. The reception, processing, usage and disposal of data are also a source of huge concern to many as AI could be used to invade privacy or to commit crimes with transnational consequences.

Government regulations can be applied as viable tools to mitigate or eradicate these harsh possibilities. However, failure to regulate AI technologies at the appropriate time or overregulation may result in dispiriting inventiveness and innovation and an undue restriction on societal advancement.

²⁷ Science Nigeria, "NITDA Seeks Stakeholders' Contribution to National AI Policy". Available online at <https://sciencenigeria.com/nitda-seeks-stakeholders-contribution-to-national-ai-policy/>. (Accessed October 13, 2022).

This paper advocate for AI Governance/Ethics in supervising the development of AI systems by governments. We have recommended that a body be set up at the national level to observe AI and determine the best approach to regulating the system. While this observation is carried out, we posit that the government can enact sector-specific laws to take care of critical areas of society that are more susceptible to the adverse effect of AI.

We believe that the application of the above propositions will result in favourable consequences for the Government, AI actors and the general public. This would ultimately result in a win-win situation for every party involved.